

EXPERIENTIAL-BASED MODULE IN NAIL CARE AND STUDENTS PERFORMANCE

HAYZEL JOY S. CAPONPON¹

ZENAIDA M. CUENCA, MAT²

16-ss-the-061@lspu.edu.ph¹

zenaida.cuenca@lspu.edu.ph²

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0040-3892>¹

Prudencia D. Fule Memorial National High School, San Pablo City Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the acceptability of the experiential-based module in nail care and its relationship to the level of performance of the student. The study utilized the descriptive-developmental design. It made use a validated questionnaire to determine the perception of the respondents on the acceptability of the experiential-based module in nail care and a validated rubrics to determine the level of students' performance. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the perception of the respondents on the acceptability of the module while the level of performance of the respondents was described using the frequency counts, percent, mean and standard deviation. The Pearson-R correlation was also used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the acceptability of the module and the students' performance in nail care. After the analysis, the study found that the experiential-based module was assessed to be highly acceptable in all evaluation areas tested. In terms of the use of the developed module, it can be inferred that the module has effectively contributed to the learning process of the students based on the result of level of their performance. Specifically, majority of the respondents were very good. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the experiential-based module in nail care is highly acceptable as perceived by the respondents. There is no significant relationship relationship of the acceptability of the module and the students' performance in nail care thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Keywords: Experiential-based, Module, Nail care, Students' Performance